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ABSTRACT

Control valves as important elements in hydraulic systems are used to transport liquid and gaseous media, for example, water, water vapor, and hydrogen. They are mainly used in the power engineering, chemical industry, and so forth. Due to their large dimensions, the verification of hydraulic parameters is problematic. In the case of liquid flow, cavitation can occur, which is mainly characterized by noise, vibrations, or changes of hydraulic parameters. During the incipient cavitation in the valve, there are no noticeable changes in the hydraulic characteristics. The article, therefore, deals with the methodology of determining the cavitation by measuring and evaluating the characteristics of the valve, spectral analysis of noise, and vibrations during water flow. Mathematical modeling is also a suitable tool for determining the extent of cavitation in valve design. Newly created modified cavitation model, where the flowing medium is defined as a mixture of incompressible water and compressible gases (vapor and air), better corresponds to physical principles than the two-phase approach (water and vapor) with experimentally modified density and viscosity. Measured noise and vibration frequency characteristics and mathematically modeled pressure frequency characteristics identify cavitation in the (1 to 10) kHz range. The article proves that when identifying cavitation, the method of measuring hydraulic characteristics fails, but the method of measuring noise and vibrations is suitable in practice, i.e., in real industrial equipment, and the modified cavitation model is suitable for identifying cavitation regions in structural designs of the hydraulic elements.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Control armatures are very important parts of thermal and nuclear power plant systems. The generation of cavitation complicates liquid flow at increasing operating conditions. Identification of cavitation is possible by various methods, i.e., experimental and mathematical methods. The most widely used experimental method is measuring the hydraulic characteristic, which is deformed in the presence of cavitation. If the cavitation region is small, the hydraulic characteristics may not be affected (Kozubková *et al.*, 2015; and Liu *et al.*, 2020). In addition, on a real device, the experimental noise and vibration measurements (Battarra and Mucchi, 2018; Mousmoulis *et al.*, 2019; and Zhao *et al.*, 2021) can be realized and evaluated by spectral analysis. Comparison of frequency characteristics during flow without cavitation and with cavitation gives information about its presence and intensity (Jablonská *et al.*, 2017; 2021).

An important experimental method is visualization, which is very illustrative. The measurement is carried out using the particle image velocimetry method or a high-speed camera. However, the transparency of the device walls is a necessary condition (Novosád *et al.*, 2021). When liquid flows through a real industrial device, the identification of cavitation is problematic, especially in incipient cavitation. The geometry of the valve causes the formation of cavitation in a very small region of flow throttling, so that the influence on the static characteristics of the hydraulic parameters is not as pronounced as, for example, in the performance of the pump discharge (Zhu *et al.*, 2019; and Mousmoulis *et al.*, 2019). Literature Kozák *et al.* (2019) provides a study on the possibilities of suppressing cavitation in industrial equipment, e.g., in pumps, turbines, by reducing erosion.

When designing new hydraulic elements of this type, verifying the functionality of new devices using computational fluid dynamics

analysis methods is expedient. Analyses of the multiphase flow of liquids and gases are time-consuming. Some publications [Liu et al. \(2020\)](#) and [Zhao et al. \(2021\)](#) deal with the simulation of the flow of water and vapor, which means two-phase flow. In many cases, the results are satisfactory. However, the mathematical model is dependent on appropriately chosen constants [Coutier-Delgosha et al. \(2003\)](#). This approach is imprecise for general geometries. Mathematical methods allow to solve the multiphase flow of liquids with cavitation and the presence of other gases, which significantly affect the flow due to their compressibility ([Jablonská et al., 2021](#); and [Zhao et al., 2021](#)). The research of a suitable mathematical model of cavitation extended by the presence of air in the liquid was solved successfully during the flow of water through a divergent-convergent nozzle with transparent walls ([Jablonská et al., 2017](#); [2021](#)). This methodology will be verified in hydraulic valves.

The article deals with the generation of cavitation in a control valve, i.e., the evaluation of hydraulic parameters during water flow in cavitation and without cavitation regimes. The article summarizes the theory of dimensionless numbers and loss coefficients typical for the armature. The static characteristics of the armature were evaluated regarding the presence of cavitation. The cavitation detection was investigated by measuring noise, and vibrations using spectral analysis. Subsequently, the flow through the armature was modeled numerically by a modified cavitation model in the ANSYS - Fluent software. The values from the experiment were used as boundary conditions for the mathematical model. Spectral analysis of pressures at various points in the area was evaluated. The results of mathematical modeling were compared with measurements in terms of static and frequency characteristics. The conclusion is focused on the evaluation of the suitability of the methods used to identify of cavitation in real hydraulic devices.

The aim of the article is to modify the cavitation mathematical model, which will not be based on tested constants and modified turbulent viscosity. The modified cavitation mathematical model is a turbulent flow model of a mixture of water, air, and vapor without the need to use experimentally determined constants. A more accurate physical principle is used in the modified cavitation model.

II. DIMENSIONLESS CHARACTERISTICS

The cavitation number σ represents the ratio of the static pressure (the difference between the inlet absolute pressure and the saturated vapor pressure) to the dynamic pressure ([Noskievič et al., 1990](#); and [Polášek et al., 2018](#)). It is defined as:

$$\sigma = \frac{p_{in} - p_w}{p_{in} - p_{out}}, \quad (1)$$

where p_{in} [Pa] is the inlet pressure, p_w [Pa] is the saturated vapor pressure, p_{out} [Pa] is the outlet pressure, according to the [IEC 60534-2-1 \(1998\)](#) standards. The smaller value of the cavitation number σ implies the greater level of cavitation ([Terentiev et al., 2011](#); [Ozonek, 2012](#); and [Jablonská et al., 2021](#)).

The air content of water is neglected in the calculations of characteristics and the liquid is presented as incompressible. According to [IEC 60534-2-1 \(1998\)](#), for nonchoked turbulent flow without attached fittings, the flow coefficient is determined by:

$$C = \frac{Q}{N_1} \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{\rho_0 \Delta p}}, \quad (2)$$

where Q is the volume flow rate, Δp is the pressure drop, ρ is the density of fluid at operational conditions, ρ_0 is the density given at reference conditions (temperature 15 °C, pressure $p = 0.1$ MPa) and N_1 numerical constant determined according to the units used, see [Table I IEC 60534-2-1 \(1998\)](#). In European countries, the flow coefficient K_v [$\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$] is mainly used.

The dimensionless loss coefficient ξ can be determined from the Bernoulli equation ([Kozubková and Jablonská, 2019](#)):

$$\Delta p = \rho \xi \frac{v^2}{2} = \rho \xi \frac{1}{2 S^2} Q^2 \Rightarrow \xi = \frac{2 S^2 \Delta p}{\rho Q^2}, \quad (3)$$

where Δp [Pa] is pressure drop, v [m s^{-1}] is velocity, Q [$\text{m}^3 \text{s}^{-1}$] is the volume flow rate, ρ [kg m^{-3}] is density, S [m^2] is the flow area. The relationship between the loss coefficient ξ and the flow coefficient K_v [$\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$] is:

$$K_v = \sqrt{\frac{2.592 \times 10^{12} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right) S^2}{\xi \rho}} \leftrightarrow \xi = \frac{2.592 \times 10^{12} \left(\frac{\rho}{\rho_0}\right) S^2}{K_v^2 \rho}. \quad (4)$$

It is often mentioned in practice dimensionless discharge coefficient ([Roček, 2002](#); and [Doubrava et al., 2019](#)):

$$C_d = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\xi}}. \quad (5)$$

III. CAVITATION

Cavitation can occur during turbulent flow in the narrowed part of the control valve under specified pressure and flow conditions. Based on the actual knowledge about cavitation, we know that it is manifested by an unexpected change in hydraulic parameters, especially, vibrations and noise, which are easily measurable.

These manifestations are caused by the so-called collapse of cavitation bubbles, which damage the important functional surfaces of the valve. In the literature [Jazi and Rahimzadeh \(2009\)](#), a methodology determining the cavitation number for full cavitation is used.

The list of influences on the formation and development of cavitation is extensive. From a technical point of view, the size and intensity of cavitation can be affected by:

- liquid properties – viscosity, surface tension, saturated vapor pressure depending on temperature,
 - flow rate,
 - the amount of dissolved and undissolved gas (air) in the liquid.
- The compressibility of the liquid mainly affects the undissolved air in the liquid.

The size of the cavitation region and acoustic manifestations generally depend on the cavitation number and valve type. For industrial practice, the following standard for defining cavitation regimes (levels)

TABLE I. Numerical constant.

	K_v	Q	Δp	ρ
N_1	0.1	[$\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$]	[kPa]	[kg m^{-3}]
N_1	1	[$\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$]	[bar]	[kg m^{-3}]

have been proposed according to ISA-RP75.23-1995 (1995), which is also described in the literature by Tullis (1989): Individual cavitation modes are defined by the range of the cavitation number, see Fig. 1.

The without cavitation mode is typical for flow through an open valve, which can change to cavitation modes when the valve is closed.

Incipient cavitation is presented by the formation of small vapor bubbles in the flowing liquid. This mode of operation is only detected in sensitive laboratory test applications or in certain biochemical processes where all evaporation must be prevented.

Constant cavitation is a moderate cavitation level that produces low levels of vibration and formation of cavities. It does not present any danger to the valve equipment. There is not noise, vibration, or damage in this state.

Incipient damage is the limit value of the cavitation number given by the manufacturer for the given valve. The value is based on experience with valve applications and is determined using a laboratory method of cavitation detection based on noise measurements.

Maximum vibrational cavitation can cause subject to heavy valve or pipeline damage, mainly if this condition occurs for a long time. Operation of the valve in this condition must be avoided.

The formation of cavitation is dangerous at reverse flow rate and rapid stoppage of flow in valves, as described in the literature Himr et al. (2019).

IV. CAVITATION IDENTIFICATION METHODS BASED ON EXPERIMENT

Commonly used methods of measuring hydraulic characteristics were performed and could show a failure trend in the presence of cavitation (Doubrava et al., 2019; Himr et al., 2019; and Jablonská et al., 2021). Method of visualization can be used in conditions of transparent walls. In the case of real devices, these visualization methods are not used.

The formation of a cavitation region is characterized by an increase in acoustic pressure intensity, which in the without cavitation case corresponds to the intensity of the turbulent flow in the armatures. In the literature Tokan (1975), it is stated that the cavitation noise depends on the size of the flow rate (flow coefficient K_v), the pressure downstream the measured armature p_2 , and the saturated vapor pressure p_w . As the pressures difference ($p_2 - p_w$) decreases, the noise level decreases, which is evident in throttling when $p_2 = p_w$, i.e., continuous evaporation occurs.

The acoustic pressure p [Pa] (its dependence on cavitation number is in Fig. 1) or the acoustic pressure level L_p [dB] is used to evaluate of the noise. Their reciprocal relationship is given in the following equation:

$$L_p = 20 \log \left(\frac{p}{p_0} \right) \quad \text{resp.} \quad p = p_0 10^{\frac{L_p}{20}}, \quad (6)$$

where the reference acoustic pressure value is $p_0 = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ Pa. The probe for noise measurement was placed in the air space outside the valve.

The power of the oscillatory process W [W] is defined as the instantaneous power for very small periods of time. The vector of acoustic intensity I [W m^{-2}] is subsequently defined as the flow of acoustic energy through a unit area in the perpendicular direction (Smetana, 1998). Acoustic intensity level L_I [dB] is:

$$L_I = 10 \log \left(\frac{I}{I_0} \right) \quad \text{resp.} \quad I = I_0 10^{\frac{L_I}{10}}, \quad (7)$$

where the reference acoustic intensity value is $I_0 = 10^{-12}$ W m^{-2} . The intensity of the noise changes depending on the size of the cavitation number.

Most analytical approaches estimate cavitation noise based on knowledge of the dynamics of the collapse of a single bubble. The resonant frequency of the noise decreases as the bubble radius increases. For the bubble radius $R_B = 1 \mu\text{m}$, the resonant frequency is 4750 MHz, but for the bubble radius $R_B = 1000 \mu\text{m}$, it is 3.29 kHz, as reported in the literature (Franc and Michel, 2005; and Yasui, 2018). For the frequency of a single bubble, the literature Brennen (2013) reports a range of natural frequencies on the order of 5 kHz to 25 kHz for nuclei occurring in water in the size range from $R_B = 1 \mu\text{m}$ to $R_B = 100 \mu\text{m}$. The noise emitted by a collapsing bubble is very rich in high harmonics whose frequency exceeds several hundred kHz (Franc and Michel, 2005).

In the literature Brennen (2013), the frequency of cavitation in the range from 6 kHz to 21 kHz is stated for the acoustic power spectrum.

If the cavitation number decreases (cavitation develops), the initial frequency is lower. Most often, cavitation noise is produced in the frequency range from 100 Hz to 100 kHz, the lower frequencies indicate the oscillation of the cavitation cloud, and the higher frequencies are caused by bubble implosions (Ozonek, 2012). In the literature Chang et al. (2023), the cavitation flow in orifice plates was investigated and it is stated that during the cavitation stage, the sound pressure level significantly increases in the high-frequency range of (500–8000) Hz, exhibiting broad-spectrum characteristics. Reducing the noise level during cavitation flow through the valve is dealt with in the literature Yu et al. (2023).

Although vibration measurement has its advantages, there is a requirement for an isolated environment from surrounding vibration sources that can disturb the measured signals. In practice, many vibration sources around the investigated element exist, such as a motor

FIG. 1. Cavitation modes.

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and pump. If we achieve the required laboratory conditions for vibration measurement, this method will quickly identify this phenomenon and its extent. Since higher frequency (5–50) kHz vibrations are in the area of interest, installing sensors on the bottom wall of the pipe (compared to the flange) will provide better information, see [ISA-RP75.23-1995 \(1995\)](#). In the literature [Siano and Panza \(2018\)](#), vibration monitoring was used to detect cavitation in a pump.

$$\int_V \int \frac{\partial(\rho\Phi)}{\partial t} dV + \int_A (\rho\Phi\vec{u} \cdot \vec{n}) dA = \int_A [\alpha_\Phi \nabla\Phi] dA + \int_V S_\Phi dV \quad (8)$$

accumulation + convection = diffusion + source,

where Φ are a general variable, and the members in the equation are sequentially convection, diffusion, and the source member, so the equation is also called convection–diffusion equation.

The flow of cavitation liquid is defined as the multiphase flow of water, vapor, and air, and therefore, the multiphase mixture model is used to modeling of cavitation. Water is assumed to be incompressible, i.e., the density of water is constant. Vapor and air are assumed as compressible gases due to large pressure changes during cavitation. The equation of state defines the densities of both gases.

The flow through the valve is turbulent, so it is necessary to use appropriate turbulence models. The most widely used model suitable for technical applications is based on the time averaged time-averaged turbulent quantities method and on the following procedure of time averaging the basic equations. The chosen two-equation renormalization group (RNG) k - ε model solves the differential equations for the turbulent time-averaged pressure and components of velocity, turbulent kinetic energy, and the turbulent dissipation rate (breakdown and extinction of turbulent vortex). These equations can be derived from the Navier–Stokes equations using a mathematical technique called the RNG method ([Orszag et al., 1993](#); [Kozubková and Jablonská, 2019](#)).

The above mathematical model was solved by the finite volume method often used in flow problems of complex geometries. A numerical simulation of the flow in the valve was performed using the ANSYS FLUENT software. The geometry was defined according to the dimensions of the device. Due to the complex geometry of the valve, the tetrahedral mesh and the method of boundary layers near the wall were used. Boundary conditions of the mass flow at the inlet to the area and the static pressure at the outlet from the area, including the mass and volume fraction of air and vapor, were determined by experiment. The without cavitation flow was investigated to test a mesh quality based on the dimensionless parameter y^+ , which did not exceed the required value according to the selected model.

For multiphase flow model calculations, cavitation effects can be included using the Schnerr and Sauer cavitation model. It is necessary to enter parameters, i.e., vaporization pressure at ambient temperature and bubble number density. The boundary conditions are extended by the mass fraction of air and vapor. Cavitation flow defines two mass transfer mechanisms—liquid-to-vapor mass transfer and vapor-to-liquid mass transfer ([Schnerr, 2001](#); and [ANSYS Fluent, 2020](#)).

V. CAVITATION IDENTIFICATION METHODS WITHOUT EXPERIMENT

The physical laws of fluid flow are the conservation laws of mass, momentum, heat, or other scalar variables. They are expressed by Navier–Stokes equations coupled with the continuity equation and energy equation, in general conservative form and describe laminar and turbulent flow regime ([Kozubková and Jablonská, 2019](#)):

The literature [Onishi et al. \(2023\)](#) defines the two-equation RNG k - ε model and improved cavitation model when considering homogeneous two-phase flow. The gas phase, consisting of vapor and noncondensable components, is assumed to be compressible and respect the equation of state. Also, in the literature [Wang et al. \(2022\)](#), the authors used the RNG k - ε turbulent model and the Schnerr and Sauer cavitation model to investigate the flow uniformity and the effect on cavitation in the control valve. The literature [Coutier-Delgosha et al. \(2003\)](#) describes a modified RNG k - ε model, which will reduce the turbulent viscosity of the mixture especially in regions with a small volume fraction. Modified viscosity models depend on experimentally determined constants that must be verified. In the case of modified model consisting of a mixture of water vapor and air, the viscosity and density are calculated based on the mixture rules.

VI. SOLUTION: THE USE OF IDENTIFICATION METHODS IN A PRACTICAL EXAMPLE

A. Experiment: Cavitation identification

The test circuit was arranged, see [Fig. 2](#). The working substance is water, which flows from the tank pos. 1 ([Fig. 2](#)) through the pump pos. 2 ([Fig. 2](#)) into the circuit. A flow meter pos. 4 ([Fig. 2](#)) measures the volume flow rate. Pressure sensors pos. 7, 8 ([Fig. 2](#)) were used to measure the relative static pressure. The position of the pressure sensor in front of the valve is $2\times$ the diameter of the pipe and the position behind the valve is $6\times$ the diameter of the pipe. Commonly available gauges were used to record the pressures, which allow measurements with a time step of 0.001 s. Acceleration (vibration) was measured by accelerometer pos. 9 ([Fig. 2](#)) located on the valve body. The microphone pos. 10 ([Fig. 2](#)) measures the noise at a distance of 30 cm perpendicular to the valve. Since we are measuring a known noise source, we can obtain a spectrum of the sound pressure level with suppressed surrounding sources (pump and electric motor). The oxygen sensor with the thermometer is in the tank, pos. 11 ([Fig. 2](#)). Test valve is a control armature DN40 - PN16 (fa ARMATURY GROUP), pos. 5 ([Fig. 2](#)), its nominal flow coefficient stated by the manufacturer $K_{v100} = 22,3 \text{ m}^3 \text{ h}^{-1}$. The manufacturer does not specify other parameters. Measurement data have been extracted from all the sensors and analyzed through a computer to evaluate unsteady turbulent flow with cavitation and averaging values of relevant variables. The parameters of the measurement

FIG. 2. Basic layout of the test circuit (1 – tank, 2 – pump with electric motor (M) regulated by a frequency converter (FM), 3 – adjusting armature at the inlet, 4 – flow meter, 5 – test valve, 6 – adjusting armature at the outlet, 7, 8 – pressure sensors, 9 – vibration sensor, 10 – noise sensor, 11 – oxygen sensor, and thermometer).

TABLE II. The parameters of the measurement instruments.

Device	Order code	Range	Extended uncertainty (%)	Sampling frequency (ms)
Flow meter	FN2014 (ELIS PLZEŇ)	$(0.72-72) \text{ m}^3\text{h}^{-1}$	± 0.5	1
Pressure sensors	PR300 (HYDROTECHNIK)	$(-1-6) \text{ bar}$	± 0.5	1
Acceleration Delta Tron	type 4507B004 (Brüel&Kjaer)	$\pm 700 \text{ m s}^{-2}$		2×10^{-5}
Microphone	MiniSPL (NTI AG)	Sensitivity 10 mV Pa^{-1}		2×10^{-5}
Sensor Oxymax (oxygen)	W COS61 (ENDRESS + HAUSER)	$(0-20) \text{ mg l}^{-1}$	± 0.3	
Sensor Oxymax (temperature)	W COS61 (ENDRESS + HAUSER)	$(-5-60) \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	± 1	

instruments are in Table II. All measurements were made at a constant water temperature of 21 °C.

1. Basic hydraulic characteristics

During the measurement, the volume flow was controlled in the range $(1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ to } 4.3 \times 10^{-3}) \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for different cone strokes, where 100% means fully open valve and 20% means opening the valve to 20%. The pressure drop was evaluated from the averaging pressure values in front of and behind the valve. Then, subsequently, dimensionless p - Q characteristics of dependence pressure drop vs volume flow rate for different valve openings with the measured error is on Fig. 3. It is evident, that the pressure loss increases with the increasing flow rate and with the closing of the valve. In the graph, the empty

points represent the flow without cavitation, i.e., without the cavitation noise. Filled points indicate the presence of cavitation noise. In the case of different closing of the valve, full cavitation did not occur, therefore, it could not be detected by the hydraulic valve characteristic (p - Q) but only by noise analysis.

Figure 4 shows the dimensionless characteristics of cavitation number vs Reynolds number at the inlet to the measured area (in the pipeline) for different valve openings. The graph confirms that the uniform incipient cavitation number cannot be determined for all valve positions. The methodology for determining the incipient cavitation number for different valve openings is based on the noise manifestations in the valve, therefore, experimentally. The cavitation number for fully developed cavitation can be determined according to the methodology in the literature Jazi and Rahinzadeh (2009).

FIG. 3. Dimensionless p - Q characteristics of pressure drop vs volume flow rate for different valve openings with the measured error plotted; (empty points = the flow without cavitation, filled points = the flow with cavitation).

FIG. 4. Cavitation number vs Reynolds number for different valve openings, where p_{in} [Pa] is the inlet pressure to the researched domain, p_w [Pa] is the saturated vapor pressure, p_{out} [Pa] is the outlet pressure from the researched domain, v_{in} [m s^{-1}] is the flow velocity at the inlet, d [m] is the characteristic dimension, and ν [$\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$] is the kinematic viscosity flowing liquid; (empty points = the flow without cavitation, filled points = the flow with cavitation).

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FIG. 5. Cavitation number vs flow coefficient, where $\Delta p = (p_m - p_{out})$ is pressure drop, Q volume flow rate; (empty points = the flow without cavitation, filled points = the flow with cavitation). ρ_1 is density of fluid at operational conditions, ρ_0 is density given at reference conditions (temperature 15 °C, pressure $p = 0.1$ MPa), p_m [Pa] is the inlet pressure to the researched domain, p_w [Pa] is the saturated vapor pressure.

Figure 5 expresses the relationship between the cavitation number and the flow coefficient. The flow coefficient has an increasing character depending on the valve opening. The flow coefficient with increasing cavitation number is almost constant for smaller openings (40%; 20%). For a larger opening (60%; 80%; 100%), it is obvious that with decreasing cavitation number, the flow coefficient increases, especially in the region of cavitation (filled points = the flow with cavitation). This is a consequence of greater losses in liquid flow with cavitation than in flow without cavitation.

The incipient cavitation in the valve was determined experimentally by noise. It does not remain constant throughout the valve opening range, it is dependent on the discharge coefficient. Sometimes the manufacturer defines a graph of the dependence of cavitation number vs discharge coefficient for different valve opening. The method for creating this graph is described in Tullis (1989). In Fig. 6, the dependence of cavitation number vs discharge coefficient for different valve closures. The cavitation number increases with the opening of the valve, whereas when the valve is fully open, cavitation occurs at higher cavitation numbers than when the valve is closed.

From figure (Figs. 4 and 5) above it was clear that at 20% opening of the valve, cavitation occurs for almost all flow rate values. Therefore, the valve with the mentioned stroke was measured in more detail.

Flow coefficient K_v from Eq. (2), loss coefficient ξ from Eq. (4) and discharge coefficient C_d from Eq. (5) are evaluated in Fig. 7. In the region of beginning cavitation (filled points), the coefficients take on constant values and do not depend on further increases in the flow rate.

FIG. 7. Flow coefficient, loss coefficient and discharge coefficient vs Reynolds number at 20% valve opening. (a) Without cavitation, (b) incipient cavitation, and (c) cavitation; (empty points = the flow without cavitation, filled points = the flow with cavitation).

From the given measurement of 20% the valve opening, the typical noise measurements are selected. In Fig. 7, they are marked by letters A, B, C. The letter A indicates the flow when no noise was heard, it can be concluded the flow was without cavitation. The letter B indicates the flow when an occasional hum was heard on the valve. The authors concluded that this is incipient cavitation. The letter C represents the variant when a continuous whistling sound was heard on the valve, therefore, this variant is marked as cavitation. The Reynolds number and cavitation number for the mentioned variants is given in Table III. The chosen variants A, B, and C for 20% opening of the valve, see Table III and Fig. 7 were further evaluated by the spectral analysis method of vibration, pressure, and noise.

TABLE III. Variants for 20% opening the valve. (5 mm stroke).

Label	Reynolds number	Cavitation number	Cavitation level
A	36 128	5.31	Without cavitation
B	72 025	1.89	Incipient cavitation
C	141 615	1.24	Cavitation

FIG. 6. Cavitation number vs discharge coefficient for different valve closures.

FIG. 8. Spectral analysis of vibration and noise; (a) without cavitation, (b) incipient cavitation, and (c) with cavitation.

2. Spectral analysis of measured noise and vibration

Spectral analysis was performed from the measured time records of noise and vibrations, and the results are evaluated in Fig. 8. The frequency range is given by Shannon Kotelnikov's theorem. Slope of a line is $(-5/3)$ (see Tüma, 2006; and Uruba, 2009).

Evaluation from pressure measurement due to the measures used does not have a meaningful value, so there is no frequency analysis of pressure in the graphs in Fig. 8 (Jablonská et al., 2017).

The measured noise is analyzed with FFT in Fig. 8 too. It can be seen that the slope of the spectrum describing the flow without cavitation (variant A - green) is the same as the slope of the theoretical curve of turbulence (dashed), which symbolizes turbulent flow vortices, as reported in the literature Uruba (2009). In the case of flow with cavitation (variant B and C), the deviation from the theoretical curve of clear turbulent flow without cavitation is evident, especially in the frequency range of 5000 Hz to 10 000 Hz, which characterizes the formation and disappearance of bubbles of different sizes.

In the case of the vibration analysis, the slope characterizing the turbulent flow with vortices are not strictly observed since pure turbulence does not cause significant vibrations of the valve wall and pipe.

The presence of cavitation can only be evaluated from vibration measurements by comparing measurements without cavitation and with cavitation when the level of acoustic intensity, velocity, or acceleration reaches higher values.

From the above results, it follows that the occurrence of cavitation is assessed from the spectral analysis of noise or vibrations. A number

of authors are engaged in experimental research on the formation of cavitation in valves with a similar range of frequencies typical for cavitation. The article Wang et al. (2024) deals with the noise caused by flow with cavitation in valves, i.e., the liquid-to-vapor phase change. The noise in these valves is generated in the frequency range (10–20) kHz. The author of the article Kazuhiko (2012) gives a frequency range of (20–8000) Hz. The literature Fu et al. (2008) describes the flow of a gate valve with cavitation flow and gives a frequency analysis of the noise up to 20 kHz.

The measurements show that cavitation occurs in the valve under certain conditions (with the increasing flow or closing the valve), but it does not indicate the area of cavitation for the needs of designers. Therefore, a detailed mathematical model of the armature was created, and a numerical simulation was performed.

B. Numerical simulation of cavitation

The geometry of the region was defined according to the dimensions of the device. For symmetry reasons, half of the 3D geometry of the DN 40 valve with a cone was used. The length of the pipe upstream and downstream the valve was chosen according to the pressure sampling points during measurement in accordance with the standard. The horizontal pipe in front of the valve was 160 mm long, and the pipe behind the valve was 240 mm long. The variant for 20% opening of the valve (stroke 5 mm) was the most interesting for modeling because at this opening, the most pronounced cavitation occurred. The

FIG. 9. Modeled valve region, monitoring point, and boundary conditions.

FIG. 10. Mesh of modeled area and details.

modeled valve area, monitoring point, and boundary conditions are shown in Fig. 9.

The tetrahedral mesh with eight boundary layers near the wall of the modeled valve region is shown in Fig. 10. The without cavitation flow was used to test the quality of the mesh. The number of mesh elements was increased until the inlet pressure did not differ from the inlet pressure at the previous mesh variant by less than 2%. The mesh with total of 3 207 363 cells was used in this case. Boundary conditions given by measurement at 20% valve opening are defined in Table IV. The turbulent intensity at the inlet and outlet is estimated to be 1% and the hydraulic diameter of inlet pipe is 0.0384 m. At the inlet, the experimentally determined mass flow rate of the mixture is defined, divided into the mass flow rate of water, the mass flow rate of air given by 2% volume fraction of air in water under atmospheric conditions and mass flow rate of vapor. The back volume fraction for vapor and air is set to zero at the outlet.

Table V shows the physical properties of the mixture used at atmospheric temperature and pressure (constant). The density and viscosity of the components (water, vapor, and air) are determined by the

TABLE IV. Boundary conditions for Variant for 20% opening the valve. (5 mm stroke).

		Water	Air	Vapor
Inlet	Mass-flow-inlet [kg s ⁻¹]	1.6356	3.958 × 10 ⁻⁵	0
Outlet	Pressure-outlet [Pa]	101 793		

TABLE V. Physical properties of flowing liquid.

	Density [kg m ⁻³]	Viscosity [Pa s]
Mixture	998.2	1.003 · × 10 ⁻³

equations for the mixture. The density of the gas (vapor and air) changes according to the equation of state during the calculation. Temperature is assumed constant. The saturated pressure for a temperature of 21 °C was set to 2360 Pa.

Following from the description in Sec. IV the RNG k-ε model including the influence of turbulent vortices decay and extinction, solves differential equations for turbulent time-averaged pressure and velocity components, turbulent kinetic energy, and turbulent dissipation rate. For cavitation Schnerr and Sauer cavitation model was used.

The task was solved as time-dependent with a time step of (5 × 10⁻⁵) s due to get solution convergence in every time step. The monitoring point (see Fig. 9) was defined near the cone wall to monitoring and recording time-dependent variables (e.g., pressure) and subsequently evaluating them by spectral analysis to identify periodic behavior.

For the given geometry, created network and boundary conditions given in Table VI, the numerical simulation deviation for the pressure calculated at the inlet was 7.9%. This shows good agreement between model and experiment.

The evaluation of contour of mean static absolute pressure and vectors of mean × velocity is shown in Fig. 11. From both views in Fig. 11, it can be seen, that cavitation occurs in the place where the pressure value is 2360 Pa [in Fig. 11(a) - blue color] and where the absolute value of x-velocity is maximal [in Fig. 11(b) - the blue color means (-22) m s⁻¹ and the red color means 22.5 m s⁻¹]. The risk of valve damage is evident in this area.

The region where cavitation occurs are better detected by the iso-surfaces of volume fraction (0.1; 0.01; 0.001) (see Fig. 12). In Table VII is calculated the volume of air, vapor, and air + vapor created in the modeled region during cavitation. The water volume is 4.11 × 10⁻⁴ m³, air and vapor are shown in Table VII. It is evident that vapor volume is smaller in comparison with air volume, which supports an application of the multiphase water-vapor-air model, as stated in the literature Jablonská et al. (2021).

For spectral analysis, a monitoring point was prepared in the model (see Fig. 9), in which pressure, volume fraction of vapor, and air were recorded. The inlet mean pressure was also recorded.

Compressible gases, i.e., air, and vapor, are dominant for the formation of cavitation. In Fig. 13, the spectral analysis of modeling

TABLE VI. Evaluation of the average pressure at the inlet.

	Experiment	Model
Inlet pressure	357 538 Pa	329 197 Pa
Deviation		7.9 %

FIG. 11. Modeled valve region. (a) Contour of mean static absolute pressure, listed in [Pa] and (b) vectors of mean x-velocity, listed in [m s^{-1}].

records is evaluated. The power spectrum slope of the vapor and air volume fraction at point [Fig. 13(a)] has the same trend as the power spectrum of turbulence, and for frequencies higher than 1000 Hz an oscillation of the spectrum expressing cavitation is visible (see red circle). On the vapor record, the oscillation is more noticeable.

In Fig. 13(b), there is a record of the pressure at the inlet, where no signs of emerging cavitation are visible due to the location of the inlet in front of the cavitation location. An increase in spectrum values can be observed on the pressure spectrum at the monitoring point near the cone, which is a consequence of cavitation.

The results of the numerical simulation give sufficient information about the presence of cavitation and the location of the cavitation region in such a geometrically complicated region as the valve. A more accurate Large Eddy Simulation turbulent model is necessary for a better comparison between experimental and modeled data. However, it requires a larger number of cells, greater demands on calculation time and computing technology.

VII. CONCLUSION

The article focuses on assessing of methods that identify cavitation in hydraulic elements during real operating conditions. The

hydraulic element under investigation was a cone valve. Hydraulic characteristics, spectral analysis of experimental pressure measurement at the inlet, noise measurement, vibration measurement, and numerical simulation of selected quantities in monitor point were used to assess cavitation. Due to the limitations of the measuring technique and the complicated geometry of the valve with the cone, it is necessary to assume that the mentioned characteristics primarily express the trend behavior of turbulent flow with cavitation.

That occur cavitation occurs under certain conditions of water flow in the valve, especially just in front of the valve closing. Due to the small cavitation region, there is no significant deformation of the hydraulic p-Q characteristic. On the contrary, in the case of other hydraulic elements, e.g., pumps, a significant deformation of the p-Q characteristic can already occur when cavitation begins. However, other methods confirm the presence of cavitation.

Evaluation of methods for identifying incipient cavitation in a valve:

1. there is no significant deformation of the hydraulic p-Q characteristic, i.e., cavitation can only be detected aurally (by noise),
2. the frequency spectrum of noise and vibration shows an increase in amplitude compared to the flow without cavitation,

FIG. 12. Isosurfaces of mean volume fraction of air, vapor, and air + vapor.

3. numerical simulation proves presence of cavitation, i.e., the region of vapor and air can be visualized, and the frequency analysis of pressure can be evaluated at points in the cavitation region, where amplitudes in the frequency spectrum of pressure again increase.

To determine the incipient cavitation, in the case of the implemented establishment, the most suitable method is the measurement of noise and, above all, vibrations when the intensity of cavitation can be determined in real-time. It can be a tool for early detection of cavitation not only in valves, but also in other hydraulic elements, especially in pumps. The noise and vibration methods are primarily based on regular measurements, comparisons, and monitoring of changes in spectral analysis and can be performed online. The contribution of the article is the recommendation of the vibration method for monitoring

the detection of cavitation as a universal method, which was suitable to be subsequently used for evaluation in artificial neural networks and to teach artificial intelligence to recognize this problem from the recording.

The numerical approach is especially advantageous for the structural design of the hydraulic element. Primarily based on the authors' experience, the article presents a new numerical simulation approach in which cavitation is modeled using water, vapor, and air. An incompressible component of water and compressible components of vapor and air are assumed in the model. The authors already used this modification for the comparison of spectral analysis in the literature [Jablonská *et al.* \(2017; 2021\)](#).

The work confirmed that numerical simulation of flow in valves is difficult due to complicated geometry, flow with turbulent vortex structures and cavitation in narrow slot flow. A new geometry and

TABLE VII. Volume fraction and volume of air, vapor, air and vapor along x axis.

air	vapor	air and vapor
$V_{\text{air}} = 6.11 \cdot 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$	$V_{\text{vapor}} = 3.44 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^3$	$V_{\text{gas}} = V_{\text{air}} + V_{\text{vapor}}$

FIG. 13. Spectral analysis of air and vapor volume fraction and pressure from numerical simulation (a) spectral analysis of volume fraction of vapor and air at point and (b) spectral analysis of pressure in inlet and at point.

mesh must be created for each investigated valve mode (lift setting). However, the multiphase flow mathematical model, cavitation model, numerical methods, and evaluation methodology can be the same for all model variants.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

Author Contributions

Jana Jablonská: Data curation (equal); Methodology (equal); Project administration (equal); Writing – original draft (equal). **Tomaš Blejchar:** Supervision (equal); Validation (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Miroslav Mahdal:** Data curation (equal); Formal analysis (equal). **Milada Kozubková:** Conceptualization (equal); Supervision (lead). **Lumír Hružík:** Funding acquisition (equal); Supervision (equal). **David Kolář:** Visualization (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12779163>, Jablonská et al. (2024).

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